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5 **Interlaboratory proficiency test in aerobiology using virtual slides – feasibility study**

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17 **Abstract**

18

19 This study examines the use of Virtual Slide Images with the aim of assessing their efficacy and
20 usability in comparison to traditional microscopy with glass slides for the Quality Control of
21 aerobiological samples. Three glass microscopy slides containing samples of airborne pollen were
22 digitised. Six counters from two laboratories examined the glass slides and their data were used to
23 calculate assigned values and acceptable coefficients of variation (CV%) for 7 pollen types. A total
24 of 24 analysts from 12 countries examined the virtual slides using specialist OlyVIA software. Data
25 from traditional glass and virtual slides were entered into tests for repeatability and
26 intralaboratory reproducibility following the norm EN 16868:2019. Participants also completed a
27 questionnaire reflecting on the efficacy and usability of Virtual Slide Images for interlaboratory
28 Quality Control. Data from traditional glass and virtual slides were comparable but coefficients of
29 variation were generally larger for virtual slides than glass slides. Participants who examined <10%
30 of the slide were more likely to produce results outside the limits of the study. The use of virtual
31 slide technology is not for everyone and, in the current study, we found that opinion was polarised
32 but it was interesting to note that there were no differences in response based on years of
33 experience. There are advantages and disadvantages of the two methods, and we recommend
34 virtual slides are used as an adjunct to glass slides for use in aerobiology Quality Control and other
35 aspects of palynological training and assessment.

36

37 *Keywords:* Aerobiology; Quality Assurance; Quality Control; Questionnaire; Virtual Slide Images

38

39 **1. Introduction**

40

41 This study was organized by the European Aerobiology Society (EAS) Working Group on Quality
42 Control which is responsible for ensuring representativeness and reproducibility of the methods
43 used in routine aerobiological monitoring. In addition to repeatability and intralaboratory
44 reproducibility the norm (EN 16868:2019 (CEN 2019)) requires regular assessment of
45 interlaboratory reproducibility and accuracy.

46 The methodology for interlaboratory Quality Control (QC) has been proposed and
47 implemented in previous large scale exercises organised under the auspices of the EAS (Galán et al.
48 2014; Šikoparija et al. 2017). However, a common feature of the former interlaboratory QC tests
49 was the time required for completion. The same sample is analysed by several pollen monitoring
50 laboratories, and so the slide needs to travel around Europe until all participants have received
51 and analysed it. This takes a great deal of time and effort (Smith et al. 2019). For example, the QC
52 exercise for *Ambrosia* pollen took a total of 531 days from when the exercise commenced until all
53 69 analysts reported their results (Šikoparija et al. 2017).

54 One method that could significantly reduce the time taken to conduct interlaboratory QC
55 tests, is virtual microscopy (Rocha et al. 2009). Virtual Slide Images (.vsi) are microscope slides that
56 have been scanned (digitalized) by taking high-resolution multi focus micrographs, which are
57 stitched together using image-processing software (Weinstein et al. 2009; Pantanowitz et al. 2011).
58 The virtual slides can be viewed on a computer screen using specialist software to examine
59 selected areas at high magnification (Koch et al. 2009; Rocha et al. 2009; Weinstein et al. 2009).
60 The technique is becoming increasingly common in research, consultation, teaching, and quality
61 control in pathology (Rocha et al. 2009; Vyas et al. 2016) and could be translated to aerobiology.

62 With this in mind, we piloted the use of Virtual Slide Images with the aim of assessing their
63 efficacy and usability in comparison to traditional microscope slides.

64

65 **2. Materials and Methods**

66

67 This project was approved by BioSense Institute Internal Review for its use of human subjects, and
68 all data have been anonymised.

69

70 *2.1. Materials for analysis*

71 In this study, segments of three 24-hour samples collected in Serbia were digitized (i.e. 11 March
72 2018, 10 August 2014, and 24 April 2018). Detailed digitalization of a 14x48mm sample is very
73 time consuming (about 30 h) and produces very large files (about 200 GB) we therefore decided to
74 only do this for the central part of the sample, i.e. a 5x48 mm section situated at about 5mm from
75 the edges of the tape. The z-axis was limited to 28 microns and 21 cross sections at 1.4 micron
76 spacing, which reduced the file size to about 25 GB (scanning time around 6h). For this purpose,
77 Olympus BX51 microscope with UPLSAPO 40x / 0.90 objective lens (180 micron working distance)
78 and Olympus Soft Imaging Solutions with XC10 digital camera were used.

79 This exercise did not aim to test the knowledge of participants and their ability to identify
80 different pollen types, rather it was to determine whether a range of different pollen types with
81 different morphological characteristics could be counted with a degree of reproducibility on
82 Virtual Slide Images.

83

84

85 2.2. *Assigned values*

86 In order to determine the correct values in the slides, six counters from two laboratories were
87 asked to analyse the microscope slides using the normal methods used in their laboratories.
88 Assigned values for selected pollen types were determined (Galán et al. 2014; Šikoparija et al.
89 2017) as the robust average after outliers were removed using Hampel's test (Šikoparija et al.
90 2017). Only pollen types with an assigned value more than 10 pollen/m³ were deemed suitable for
91 further analysis (CEN 2019).

92

93 2.3. *Virtual slides between analysts comparison*

94 A call for participation in this QC exercise was sent by the European Aerobiology Society's QC
95 Working Group to active aerobiological monitoring stations in Europe. Virtual slides were analysed
96 using the Olympus OlyVIA ver.2.9.1 build 13771 software (freely available from
97 <https://www.olympus-lifescience.com/en/support/downloads/>). Participants were requested to
98 analyse a minimum of 10% of the slide surface using a magnification they felt comfortable with
99 (Galán et al. 2014). The analysed surface depends on the size of the display and so participants
100 were asked to submit a screenshot of the display, after choosing the magnification they wanted to
101 use, so that the area of slide examined in pixels could be verified. A list of pollen types likely to be
102 found on each slide (not exhaustive) was supplied to counters to aid identification (Appendix 1).

103

104 2.4. *Questionnaires*

105 Participants were asked to fill in a questionnaire reflecting on the efficacy and usability of Virtual
106 Slide Images for interlaboratory Quality Control. The questionnaire included 7 questions on a
107 Likert Scale of 1 to 7 (ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree) and based on similar

108 studies in literature (Blake et al. 2003; Burthem et al. 2005; Koch et al. 2009; Evered & Dudding
109 2011; Hanna et al. 2019):

110 1. The Virtual Slide Images and OlyVIA software were easy to install;

111 2. The guidance and supporting material provided were sufficient for helping me prepare for the
112 QC exercise;

113 3. The OlyVIA software was easy to use;

114 4. The manoeuvrable images studied with the OlyVIA software were of sufficient resolution to
115 allow identification of pollen;

116 5. The ability to conduct the laboratory exercise on my own schedule with the computer
117 technology was an advantage;

118 6. Navigating the images with the computer and OlyVIA software was easier than that of glass
119 slides with a microscope;

120 7. The computer technology saved me time compared to using light microscopy.

121 There were also questions about gender and the number of years of experience counting pollen
122 (< 5 years, 5-10 years and >10 years). In addition, the questionnaire included two open ended
123 questions where participants could say what they liked most about using Virtual Slide Images and
124 their suggestions for improving the system.

125

126 2.5. *Data analysis*

127 The results from the analyses of Virtual Slide Images were examined in relation to coefficients of
128 variation (CV%) as described in EN 16868:2019 (CEN 2019) and z-scores as presented in previous
129 QC studies of aerobiological data (Galán et al. 2014; Šikoparija et al. 2017). Acceptable coefficients
130 of variation were calculated based on the assigned values determined from the analysis of

131 microscope slides (CEN 2019). Questionnaire data were analysed using the non-parametric
132 Kruskal–Wallis one-way analysis of variance to determine if there were significant differences
133 between responses based on the number of years of experience counting pollen. Results were
134 deemed significant with a p -value < 0.05 . The analysis packages used were Microsoft® Excel for
135 Mac Version 16.32 and SPSS 26.

136

137 **3. Results**

138

139 *3.1. Assigned values and tests for repeatability and intralaboratory reproducibility*

140 Six counters from two laboratories: Laboratory for palynology University of Novi Sad Faculty of
141 Sciences, Serbia (Lab A) and Belgian Institute for Health, Sciensano (Lab B), examined microscope
142 Slide 1 (11-03-2018) and microscope Slide 2 (10-08-2019). Following analysis of the microscope
143 slides, assigned values were determined for *Alnus*, *Ambrosia*, *Artemisia*, *Corylus*,
144 Cupressaceae/Taxaceae, Poaceae and Urticaceae. The acceptable coefficients of variation (CV%)
145 were calculated for each pollen type. One daily average Urticaceae pollen concentration from Lab
146 A was deemed to be an outlier following the Hampel test and was removed from the analysis and
147 not used for calculating the assigned value (Table I).

148 Repeatability was tested using data from the glass slides for one counter from Lab A as
149 defined in the norm EN 16868:2019 (Section 8.4.2)(CEN 2019): one slide; same analyst; same
150 method; minimum three replicates per analyst. All results were within the acceptable coefficients
151 of variation for each pollen type (Table I).

152 Intralaboratory reproducibility was examined using data from the glass slides for Lab A, Lab
153 B and all laboratory staff together following EN 16868:2019 (Section 8.4.3), with the same

154 acceptable coefficients of variation used as those for repeatability (CEN 2019). The majority of
155 results were within the acceptable coefficients of variation for each pollen type. There was one
156 result for Cupressaceae/Taxaceae that was outside acceptable limits from Lab B (CV% of 34). As
157 previously mentioned, one participant from Lab A also reported an anomalously low Urticaceae
158 pollen concentration and this was removed as an outlier (before it was removed the CV% for Lab A
159 and all labs together was > 10) (Table I).

160 Following the norm (CEN 2019), only pollen types with an assigned value more than 10
161 pollen/m³ were deemed suitable for further analysis. Poaceae had an assigned value of 9
162 pollen/m³ and as a result should not have been examined further, but it is interesting to note that
163 the CV% was greater than 30 for all tests of repeatability and intralaboratory reproducibility for
164 this pollen type (Table I).

165

166 3.2. *Virtual slides between analysts comparison*

167 A total of 24 analysts (Appendix 2) participated in the study from 12 countries (Belgium, France,
168 Germany, Italy, Lithuania, Netherlands, Portugal, Serbia, Slovakia, Spain, Switzerland, Turkey). We
169 initially gave participants 2 months to submit their results, but this deadline was extended for an
170 additional month because of a number of delays. The first information was received within one
171 month of commencing the exercise. Most data were delivered during the third month of the
172 exercise after the deadline was extended.

173 Data from Virtual Slide Images were compared to the assigned values and thresholds for
174 acceptable coefficients of variation (CV%) calculated from examining microscope slides. Results of
175 the analyses are shown in Figures 1–7, both for acceptable coefficients of variation (CV%) as used
176 in tests for repeatability and intralaboratory reproducibility following the norm EN 16868:2019

177 (CEN 2019) and z-scores as described in previous exercises carried out by the European
178 Aerobiology Society Working Group on Quality Control (Galán et al. 2014; Šikoparija et al. 2017).

179 Four of the counters who analysed the microscope slides also analysed virtual slides (QC1,
180 QC8, QC9, and QC10). The change to virtual slides did not noticeably affect their performance, as
181 all of their results were within the limits of CV% for pollen types with an assigned value >10
182 pollen/m³. On the whole, however, coefficients of variation were generally larger for virtual slides
183 than glass slides.

184 A number of results for each pollen type exceeded the CV thresholds, and from the data it
185 was possible to identify several potential errors in identification. For example, participant QC15
186 appeared to have mis-identified a pollen type as being *Artemisia* (Fig. 3), participant QC16 seemed
187 to count the majority of *Corylus* as *Betula* (Fig. 4) and participants QC6 and QC18 counted
188 Urticaceae as Cannabaceae (Fig. 7).

189 The area of the virtual slides analysed by participants had a notable impact on the results.
190 Better results were achieved if a larger area of the slide was analysed. Four counters (QC1, QC2,
191 QC3 and QC4) analysed the whole of the virtual slide surface (100% of the virtual slide and ~36%
192 of the original glass slide) and generally recorded low CV%. A total of 8 out of the 24 participants
193 (33%) examined <10% of the surface of the slides (<10% of the whole slide, not just the virtual
194 slide). It was observed that 24 results exceeded the limits of the study and 12 of these (50%) were
195 from participants who examined <10% of the slide (Figs 1–7).

196

197 3.3. User opinion

198 All 24 participants responded to the questionnaire survey. Seventeen respondents were female
199 and 7 were male. Seven respondents had less than 5 years' experience counting pollen, 5
200 respondents had between 5 and 10 years' experience and 11 had more than 10-years' experience

201 counting pollen (1 respondent did not answer this question). The results of questionnaire (Fig. 8)
202 show that the majority (>70%) of respondents agreed that the Virtual Slide Images and OlyVIA
203 software were easy to install, the guidance and supporting material provided were sufficient for
204 helping them prepare for the QC exercise, the OlyVIA software was easy to use and having the
205 ability to conduct the laboratory exercise on their own schedule with the computer technology
206 was an advantage. Responses were particularly positive about the guidance and supporting
207 material (87.5% agreed). Less people agreed that the manoeuvrable images studied with the
208 OlyVIA software were of sufficient resolution to allow identification of pollen (62.5%). There were
209 fewer positive responses (<30%) when people were asked about the ease of navigating the images
210 with the computer and OlyVIA software and whether the computer technology saved them time
211 compared to using light microscopy. The results of the Kruskal Wallis test showed there were no
212 significant differences in responses based on years of experience.

213 When participants were asked what they liked most about using Virtual Slide Images, over
214 a third mentioned advantages of using the computer rather than a microscope. These included the
215 possibility of more than one person being able view the same image at the same time, the large
216 field of view, ease of handling and that there was no time pressure and they were able to perform
217 the analysis anywhere at any time. In addition, several respondents recognised that virtual slides
218 could potentially save time compared to a traditional QC exercise and highlighted the fact that
219 virtual slides could not be damaged and can be permanently stored.

220 On the other hand, three respondents had nothing positive to say about the Virtual Slide
221 Images (they responded to both open ended questions, but all their responses were negative).
222 Suggestions for improving the use of Virtual Slide Images were primarily concerned with the focus
223 (z-axis) and the manoeuvrability of the slide image (x- and y-axis). Comments largely supported
224 the answers to the Likert scale questions, with several participants complaining the virtual slides

225 took longer to analyse (one respondent saying that one slide had taken all day) and that it was not
226 as ergonomically comfortable as sitting at a microscope.

227

228 3.4 Technical difficulties

229 Slide 3 (24-04-2019) was removed from the study because of reported problems in the way the
230 images were stitched together in the virtual slide and because some participants complained that
231 analysis was rather complicated due to the fact that not all pollen types on Slide 3 were
232 frequently encountered in all parts of Europe (Appendix 1). A common complaint was that the
233 slide images were too large and took too long to download. Approximately one third of
234 participants reported problems with focussing, including blurry images.

235

236 **4. Discussion**

237

238 The digital capture of glass slide preparations to produce Virtual Slide Images is still a relatively
239 new technology (Evered & Dudding 2011). Although digital slides are increasingly being employed
240 in medicine for the teaching and assessment of histology and pathology (Vyas et al. 2016) and can
241 also be used for training, intralaboratory quality control, interlaboratory quality assurance and
242 image analysis (Rocha et al. 2009; Evered & Dudding 2011). Digital images are not expensive to
243 duplicate, they do not deteriorate, break or disappear, they are easy to store and are available to
244 multiple users simultaneously (Koch et al. 2009; Pantanowitz et al. 2011).

245 Light microscopy using traditional glass slides, on the other hand, is the established tool in
246 aerobiology (Oteros et al. 2015) and can be considered the gold standard for the analysis of
247 aerobiological samples. There are certain advantages to traditional microscopy, as analysts are

248 familiar with the equipment and have full control of XYZ stages, and glass slides are cheap to
249 prepare (Evered & Dudding 2011). However, glass slides are easily broken (Evered & Dudding
250 2011) which is a potential problem when conducting large scale interlaboratory QC exercises
251 where samples are sent to multiple sites (Galán et al. 2014; Šikoparija et al. 2017).

252

253 4.1 *Virtual slides between analysts comparison*

254 In this investigation, glass slide microscopy was considered to be the gold standard as described
255 for previous studies related to dermatitis and pathology (Koch et al. 2009; Vyas et al. 2016). The
256 results from the glass slides produced by one analyst were examined for repeatability and all data
257 from counters who used traditional microscopy were included in tests for intralaboratory
258 reproducibility following the norm EN 16868:2019 (CEN 2019). In addition, a total of 24 analysts
259 participated in between analyst comparisons using Virtual Slide Images. It was found that data
260 from traditional glass and virtual slides were comparable but coefficients of variation were
261 generally larger for virtual slides than glass slides. Some of this variation could be attributed to
262 reported problems with focusing the OlyVIA software and analysts coming into contact with pollen
263 types they were not normally accustomed to seeing. However, the results allowed identification of
264 several possible errors in identification, thereby highlighting the potential for the system to be
265 used in training and Quality Control.

266 It was noticeable that 33% of participants looked at less than 10% of the slide but made up
267 50% of results that were outside of the limits of the study. This is not particularly surprising as a
268 number of studies have now highlighted the fact that the area of the slide examined has a
269 significant impact on the quality of the data produced (Galán et al. 2014; Šikoparija et al. 2017;
270 Smith et al. 2019). This is further evidence that networks should follow the recommendations that
271 analysts should examine at least 10% of the slide surface (Mandrioli et al. 1998; Šikoparija et al.

272 2011; Galán et al. 2014). In addition, Poaceae had an assigned value of <10 pollen/m³ and a CV%
273 greater than 30 for all tests of repeatability and intralaboratory reproducibility, thereby
274 highlighting the importance of selecting pollen types that are present on the slides in sufficient
275 numbers (Šikoparija et al. 2017; Smith et al. 2019).

276

277 4.2 *User opinion*

278 Participants were invited to give their opinion on the efficacy and usability of digital slides. On a
279 positive note, participants were satisfied with the amount of guidance and supporting material
280 provided, and generally agreed that the virtual slides and OlyVIA software were easy to install and
281 use. However, it is known that one disadvantage of digital microscopy is the large amount of
282 digital storage space needed for image data (Vyas et al. 2016). Indeed, several participants
283 commented that they experienced problems when downloading the slides because of their size.

284 Results of the questionnaire survey showed that many participants also liked the fact that
285 they could conduct the exercise in their own time. Moreover, participants mentioned the benefit
286 of being able to examine and discuss the slides with colleagues. This highlights the potential of
287 using Virtual Slide Images as a training tool.

288 The survey did, however, identify some issues with the usability of the system and
289 respondents were not impressed by the ability of the OlyVIA software to navigate around the
290 slides and did not think the virtual slides saved time compared to traditional glass slides. This is in
291 agreement with a previous study conducted by Vyas et al. (2016) who compared whole slide
292 digital images and traditional glass slides in the detection of common microscopic features seen in
293 dermatitis. The authors observed the efficiency of using glass slides was superior to digital slides,
294 and that glass slides were generally read faster (Vyas et al. 2016). Hanna et al. (2019) also
295 witnessed a 19% decrease in efficiency (increase in turnaround time) using digital pathology slides.

296 It should be remembered, however, that virtual slides are not meant to test all microscope
297 skills as field selection and focussing with virtual slides has been likened to operating a camera
298 (Burthem et al. 2005). With this in mind, it is important to note that more than 60% of participants
299 in the current study agreed there was sufficient resolution to allow identification of pollen.
300 Similarly, Blake et al. (2003) described the successful change from using traditional microscopes
301 and glass slides to using virtual slides. In their study the authors reported that, when asked, the
302 vast majority of medical students on the histology course they delivered rated digital images as
303 having excellent resolution (Blake et al. 2003).

304

305 4.3. Evaluation

306 Rocha et al. (2009) defined digital slide quality by the following factors: (A) Quality - condition of
307 the original slide; (B) Completeness - the slide should be accessible in its entirety; (C) Image quality
308 - attributes of the digital slide (e.g. sharpness, contrast, colour) should be comparable to those of a
309 real microscope; (D) Usability – such as smooth scrolling and magnification options.

310 The quality of the scanned slide is important (Rocha et al. 2009) but so is the spectrum of
311 pollen types present and previous QC exercises have focused on only a few regionally important
312 allergenic pollen (Galán et al. 2014; Šikoparija et al. 2017). It was clear that a number of
313 participants struggled with the sample on Slide 3 collected in Serbia during the Spring of 2018,
314 which contained pollen types with similar morphological characteristics such as *Broussonetia*,
315 *Celtis*, *Morus*, and *Urticaceae* (Appendix 1). These pollen types are not commonly encountered in
316 large numbers in all parts of Europe, and this contributed to Slide 3 being omitted from the final
317 analysis. It should also be remembered that different aerobiological laboratories use different
318 methods, which include a variety of staining agents that result in pollen of different hues (or no
319 stain at all) and a range of adhesives that can make slides look different. Indeed, one participant

320 did mention that the colouration of the slides made it difficult to identify the pollen. Analysts
321 become accustomed to the techniques used in their own labs and this needs to be considered in
322 interlaboratory QC tests and compromises made. However, there should also be recognition that
323 you cannot please everyone all the time.

324 In an attempt to reduce the size of the virtual image, only part of the exposed portion of
325 the slide (5x48mm) was digitised. This is, however, the area typically examined during routine
326 monitoring using longitudinal transects (e.g. Galán et al. (2007)). Assigned values were calculated
327 using the data from the glass slides. This allowed us to compare counts made from traditional
328 glass slides with those from and Virtual Slide Images, although the results show there was more
329 variation in the data from virtual slides than traditional glass slides.

330 The quality of all images is extremely important when using virtual slides as a testing tool
331 (Koch et al. 2009). The high-resolution multi focus micrographs used in this study were generally of
332 sufficient resolution for the identification of pollen, but there were limitations and participants
333 often requested improvements in this regard. Problems related to the stitching together of the
334 images also caused Slide 3 to be omitted from the study.

335 The usability of the current system is also rather limited, and the ultimate goal would be
336 for technology that can rapidly upload images, proficiently focus, and effortlessly navigate across
337 virtual slides in the same way as operators do with glass slides (Koch et al. 2009). In order to make
338 the files used in this study acceptable for online transfer, the size of the files had to be reduced
339 and the image spacing of the z-stack restricted (i.e. 28 microns with 20 layers at 1.4 micron step).
340 The results of our study indicate that, for more precise identification of pollen where fine
341 morphological features need to be seen, a thicker z-stack with finer step must be used. This is
342 particularly important in melissopalynology. As a result, much larger files would need to be
343 produced for use in quality control following the norm DIN 10760: 2002 (DIN 2002) for the

344 determination of the relative frequency of pollen in the analysis of honey. For smooth online views
345 of virtual slide images the application of a client-server-based data management system such as
346 the Net Image Server SQL would be needed ([https://www.olympus-](https://www.olympus-lifescience.com/en/microscopes/virtual/vs120/net-image-server-sql/)
347 [lifescience.com/en/microscopes/virtual/vs120/net-image-server-sql/](https://www.olympus-lifescience.com/en/microscopes/virtual/vs120/net-image-server-sql/)).

348 The use of virtual slides as a tool for quality assurance programmes has certain advantages,
349 not least the ability to distribute identical images from a single original slide to multiple users at
350 different sites thereby avoiding the problems and costs related to sending slides between
351 laboratories by post (Burthem et al. 2005; Rocha et al. 2009). Such exercises can customarily take
352 months to complete, as shown in aerobiology (Šikoparija et al. 2017) and other disciplines such as
353 pathology (Rocha et al. 2009). Whereas, in this study, all data were returned within three months.

354 It is important that participants in proficiency tests examine the same material, and there is
355 potential for the use of digital slides in quality control programmes and for measuring accuracy
356 (Rocha et al. 2009). For instance, in a pilot study assessing the use of virtual slides in
357 haematological quality assessment, Burthem et al. (2005) reported comparable results from both
358 glass and digital slides. As a result, the authors recommended that digital virtual slides could be
359 used as a supplementary resource to glass slides in educational aspects of haematological
360 morphology and external quality assessment (Burthem et al. 2005). However, the use of virtual
361 slide technology is not for everyone and, in the current study, we have found that opinion was
362 polarised but it was interesting to note that there were no differences in response based on years
363 of experience. Both traditional glass and virtual slides test common skills such as identification,
364 and it is recognised there are advantages and disadvantages of the two (Burthem et al. 2005; Koch
365 et al. 2009). We therefore recommend that, as with the study by Burthem et al. (2005), virtual
366 slides are used as an adjunct to glass slides for use in aerobiology quality control and other aspects
367 of palynological training and assessment.

368

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370

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375

376 **Figure Legends**

377

378 Figure 1. Results between analyst comparison using virtual slides for *Alnus*: (A) Acceptable
379 coefficients of variation(CV%) as used for repeatability and intralaboratory reproducibility
380 following the norm EN 16868:2019; (B) z-scores as described in previous exercises carried out by
381 the European Aerobiology Society Working Group on Quality Control (Galán et al. 2014; Sikoparija
382 et al. 2017). Results from participants who examined <10% of the digital slide marked in bold.

383

384 Figure 2. Results between analyst comparison using virtual slides for *Ambrosia*: (A) Acceptable
385 coefficients of variation(CV%) as used for repeatability and intralaboratory reproducibility
386 following the norm EN 16868:2019; (B) z-scores as described in previous exercises carried out by
387 the European Aerobiology Society Working Group on Quality Control (Galán et al. 2014; Sikoparija
388 et al. 2017). Results from participants who examined <10% of the digital slide marked in bold.

389

390 Figure 3. Results between analyst comparison using virtual slides for *Artemisia*: (A) Acceptable
391 coefficients of variation(CV%) as used for repeatability and intralaboratory reproducibility
392 following the norm EN 16868:2019; (B) z-scores as described in previous exercises carried out by

393 the European Aerobiology Society Working Group on Quality Control (Galán et al. 2014; Sikoparija
394 et al. 2017). Results from participants who examined <10% of the digital slide marked in bold.

395

396 Figure 4. Results between analyst comparison using virtual slides for *Corylus*: (A) Acceptable
397 coefficients of variation(CV%) as used for repeatability and intralaboratory reproducibility
398 following the norm EN 16868:2019; (B) z-scores as described in previous exercises carried out by
399 the European Aerobiology Society Working Group on Quality Control (Galán et al. 2014; Sikoparija
400 et al. 2017). Results from participants who examined <10% of the digital slide marked in bold.

401

402 Figure 5. Results between analyst comparison using virtual slides for Cupressaceae/Taxaceae: (A)
403 Acceptable coefficients of variation (CV%) as used for repeatability and intralaboratory
404 reproducibility following the norm EN 16868:2019; (B) z-scores as described in previous exercises
405 carried out by the European Aerobiology Society Working Group on Quality Control (Galán et al.
406 2014; Sikoparija et al. 2017). Results from participants who examined <10% of the digital slide
407 marked in bold.

408

409 Figure 6. Results between analyst comparison using virtual slides for Poaceae: (A) Acceptable
410 coefficients of variation (CV%) as used for repeatability and intralaboratory reproducibility
411 following the norm EN 16868:2019; (B) z-scores as described in previous exercises carried out by
412 the European Aerobiology Society Working Group on Quality Control (Galán et al. 2014; Sikoparija
413 et al. 2017). Results from participants who examined <10% of the digital slide marked in bold.

414

415 Figure 7. Results between analyst comparison using virtual slides for Urticaceae: (A) Acceptable
416 coefficients of variation (CV%) as used for repeatability and intralaboratory reproducibility
417 following the norm EN 16868:2019; (B) z-scores as described in previous exercises carried out by

418 the European Aerobiology Society Working Group on Quality Control (Galán et al. 2014; Sikoparija
419 et al. 2017). Results from participants who examined <10% of the digital slide marked in bold.

420

421 Figure 8. Results of the questionnaire study to participants involved in the interlaboratory
422 proficiency test using virtual slides (% responses)

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485 Table I. Assigned values and results of repeatability and intralaboratory reproducibility as defined
 486 in the norm (EN 16868:2019). **SPT** (standard deviation for proficiency testing = Robust standard
 487 deviation); **Assigned value** (Assigned value (X) = robust average); **n** = Datasets after the removal of
 488 outliers (Hampel test); **1 counter CV%** = Repeatability; **Lab A CV%** = Laboratory A
 489 Intralaboratory Reproducibility; **Lab B CV%** = Laboratory B Intralaboratory Reproducibility; **All**
 490 **CV%** = All counter Intralaboratory Reproducibility; **Allowed CV%** = The acceptable coefficients
 491 of variation (CV)
 492

Pollen type	SPT	Assigned value	n =	1 counter CV%	Lab A CV%	Lab B CV%	All CV%	Allowed CV%
<i>Alnus</i>	6.12	42	8	19	19	5	15	20
<i>Ambrosia</i>	9.01	83	8	12	12	3	11	20
<i>Artemisia</i>	2.58	23	8	3	5	4	11	30
<i>Corylus</i>	4.61	34	8	15	12	18	14	20
[†] Cup/Tax	6.26	25	8	14	22	34	25	30
Poaceae	2.81	9	8	33	33	31	32	NA
Urticaceae	18.61	349	7	3	3*	4	5*	10

493 [†]Cupressaceae/Taxaceae

494 *Outliers removed (Hampel test)

495 Repeatability - EN 16868:2019 CV% (Section 8.4.2)

496 Intralaboratory Reproducibility - EN 16868:2019 CV% (Section 8.4.3)

497 The acceptable coefficients of variation (CV), calculated only for taxa with an assigned value > 10

498 EN 16868:2019 CV% (Section 8.4.2).

499

(A)

(B)

(A)

(B)

(A)

(B)

507

508

(A)

(B)

(A)

(B)

(A)

(B)

(A)

(B)

521 Figure 8

522

523

524 **Appendices**

525 **Appendix 1**

526 The list of pollen types likely to be found on each slide (not exhaustive), which was supplied to
527 counters to aid identification:

- 528 • Slide 1 (11-03-2018): *Alnus*, *Corylus*, *Fraxinus*, *Populus*, Taxaceae/Cupressaceae, *Ulmus*.
- 529 • Slide 2 (10-08-2014): *Ambrosia*, Apiaceae, *Artemisia*, Cannabaceae, Chenopodiaceae, *Plantago*
530 Poaceae, Urticaceae, *Xanthium*.
- 531 • Slide 3 (24-04-2018): *Alnus*, Apiaceae, *Betula*, Brassicaceae, *Broussonetia*, *Carpinus*, *Celtis*,
532 Cyperaceae, *Fagus*, *Fraxinus*, *Juglans*, *Morus*, Pinaceae, *Platanus*, Poaceae, *Quercus*, *Rumex*,
533 *Salix*, Taxaceae/Cupressaceae, Urticaceae.

534

535 **Appendix 2**

536 The following counters participated in this QC exercise: Arandjelovic, A.; Bekil, S.; Bruffaerts, N.;
537 Bucher, E.; Cislighi, G.; de Weger, L.; Dovydaityte, D.; Kolek, F.; Graber, M-J.: Hoebeke, L.; Iannotta,
538 M.P.; Leier-Wirtz, V.; Martínez-Bracero, M.; Navarro, D.; Oliver, G.; Pereira, C.; Pereira, J.; Plaza,
539 M.; Radisic, P.; Ribeiro, H.; Sallin, C; Ščevková, J.; Šikoparija, B.; Trajkovska, G.; Tosunoglu, A.;
540 Verstraeten, C.

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